

Preliminary study on the application of 3D-printed resin for joints in round bamboo structures

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Abstract

This study investigates the feasibility of using 3D-printed resin joints in round bamboo structures. First, fundamental mechanical tests were conducted to evaluate the compression, tensile, and shear properties of carbon fiber-reinforced 3D-printed resin. The results showed that the compression strength of the resin plateaus at an infill density of approximately 60%, making this density the most efficient for structural applications. Next, mechanical tests on simple joint configurations were performed. A compression joint utilizing bearing stress at the bamboo culm cross-section exhibited higher strength than the resin alone, suggesting that standalone resin tests can provide a conservative strength estimate. Additionally, a single-shear screw connection between the bamboo culm wall and 3D-printed resin achieved a shear resistance comparable to wood-based materials. The failure mode was radial splitting at the screw-culm contact area, and some results closely matched ISO 22156 strength predictions. This study highlights the potential of 3D-printed joints for bamboo structures and aims to integrate digital fabrication techniques into large-scale bamboo components, such as trusses and columns, in future research.

Keywords: bamboo structures, round bamboo, full-culm bamboo, joints, 3d-print, digital fabrication, carbon-fiber-reinforced resin.

1. Introduction

Bamboo, in addition to its excellent mechanical properties, possesses a short harvesting cycle, strong regenerative capacity, and remarkable carbon sequestration ability, making it a material with significant potential as a sustainable building material. As the world moves towards the realization of a carbon-neutral society, bamboo is increasingly anticipated as one of the viable options for construction materials, and the momentum for international research and development is growing. However, there remain numerous issues in utilizing bamboo as a structural material. One of the major issues in round bamboo (full-culm bamboo) structures is the development of joints. Joints not only require high mechanical performance but must also be capable of accommodating the naturally irregular shapes of bamboo culms and be easy to install.

Although many joint designs for round bamboo structures have been proposed, they either suffer from significantly lower strength and stiffness compared to the bamboo itself due to their primitive design, or are mechanically excellent but extremely complex to construct, and thus, no definitive international standard has yet been established (e.g., Widyowijatnoko and Harries [1]). Therefore, we investigate the use of 3D-printed resin, reinforced with carbon fiber, for joints. The use of a 3D printer allows for the easy adaptation of the joint to the varying sizes and shapes of bamboo culms, and the small-scale production of joints is feasible without location constraints, as long as a compact printer is available.

In this study, we first examine the fundamental mechanical properties of 3D-printed carbon fiber-reinforced resin. Subsequently, we conduct mechanical tests on joint specimens, assuming their application in real round bamboo structures. Furthermore, we compare the experimental results with theoretical strength estimations derived from existing joint strength formulas, analyzing the failure mechanisms and evaluating the structural performance of the joints.

2. Materials and methods

Various methods exist for 3D printing, and when mechanical performance and durability are required for the printed object, Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM) is commonly used. This method involves mechanically feeding a resin filament into the output nozzle, where it is melted by heat and extruded layer by layer to form the printed object. Consequently, the printed object develops layering planes at regular intervals parallel to the build plate, which introduces strong anisotropy in the mechanical properties of the printed resin. The variations in mechanical properties across different directions exhibit characteristics similar to those of wood.

Fig. 1 presents a diagram illustrating the anisotropy of 3D-printed resin fabricated using the FDM method. In the figure, the “out-of-layer direction” (OLD) represents the direction in which the layers are stacked during 3D printing, which is perpendicular to the build plate. The “in-layer direction” (ILD) is defined as the direction perpendicular to the out-of-layer direction, meaning it is parallel to the build plate. In this study, the two orthogonal axes within the in-layer direction are defined as X and Y directions, while the out-of-layer direction is defined as the Z direction. Additionally, when the infill pattern is set to either “triangular” or “gyroid”, there is minimal difference in the mechanical properties along the X-Y directions. This characteristic suggests that, compared to wood, 3D-printed resin is easier to handle in engineering applications, making it advantageous for practical use.

Figure 1. Definition of directions and anisotropy in 3d-printed resin.

Table 1. Mechanical properties of the filament material in dried condition [2].

Mechanical property	Standard	XY (ILD)	XZ (ILD)	ZX (OLD)
Tensile strength [MPa]	ISO 527	103.2	-	18.2
Young's modulus [MPa]	ISO 527	8386	-	3532
Flexural strength [MPa]	ISO 178	160.7	171.8	50.8
Flexural modulus [MPa]	ISO 178	8258	7669	2715

The resin filament used in this study is PAHT CF15 (manufactured by BASF), a carbon fiber-reinforced filament with pre-mixed carbon fibers. The 3D printer used for fabrication is Raise 3D Pro2 Plus (manufactured by Raise 3D). Table 1 presents selected representative mechanical properties of the filament material [2]. The fundamental mechanical performance of the resin used in this study is comparable to or higher than that of wood-based materials and bamboo (Nagai [3]). Additionally, the resin exhibits high heat resistance, and its performance is expected to remain largely unaffected by normal temperature fluctuations. Therefore, it holds promise as a potential material for joint components in bamboo structures.

3. Mechanical testing of 3D-printed resin

3.1. Testing methods

Fig. 2 illustrates the mechanical testing methods used in this study. Since the 3D-printed resin is intended for use in bamboo structure joints, the mechanical tests are based on ISO 5257 [4], which outlines mechanical testing methods for engineered bamboo products using small specimen samples. However, due to constraints in the testing apparatus and specimen fabrication, some dimensions were adjusted. The parameters considered in the mechanical testing of the resin are as follows: (1) the relationship between the layering direction and the loading direction, (2) the infill pattern, (3) the infill density. For compression and tensile tests, loading was applied in two directions: in-layer (ILD) and out-of-layer (OLD). For shear tests, three loading conditions were examined: in-plane shear within the in-layer surface (ILD), in-layer direction shear on the out-of-layer surface (ILD-OLS), and out-of-layer direction shear on the out-of-layer surface (OLD-OLS).

Figure 2. Mechanical testing methods for 3d-printed resin.

Table 2. List of parameters considered in mechanical testing of 3d-printed resin.

Compression test			Tensile test			Shear test		
IFP	IFD [%]	Direction	IFP	IFD [%]	Direction	IFP	IFD [%]	Plane-direction
Gyroid	37	ILD	Gyroid	37	ILD	Triangular	37	ILS
		OLD			OLD		60	
Triangular	37	ILD	Triangular	60	ILD	Triangular	37	OLS-ILD
		OLD			ILD		60	
Triangular	60	ILD	Triangular	75	ILD	Triangular	37	OLS-OLD
		OLD			ILD		60	
Triangular	75	ILD	IFD: infill density, IFP: infill pattern, ILD: in-layer direction, OLD: out-of-layer direction, ILS: in-layer surface, OLS: out-of-layer surface					
		OLD						

The infill pattern was varied between two configurations: triangular and gyroid. Under identical infill density and volume conditions, specimens printed with these infill patterns have nearly equivalent mass. The infill density was varied at three levels: 37%, 60%, and 75%, and the differences in mechanical properties were examined. However, due to geometrical constraints in specimen fabrication and technical limitations in 3D printing, certain parameter combinations were challenging to print and were thus omitted from evaluation.

To ensure consistency, when comparing a specific parameter, all corresponding specimens were printed simultaneously to eliminate potential variations caused by differences in filament condition, temperature, or humidity. The layer thickness for printing was set to 0.2 mm for all specimens.

3.2. Compression test results

Fig. 3(a) presents the results for specimens printed with a triangular infill pattern at varying infill densities, while Fig. 4 shows photographs of the specimens after testing. The legend in the figure denotes “OLD” : out-of-layer direction and “ILD” : in-layer direction. The horizontal axis represents strain, which is calculated as the displacement of the testing machine simply divided by the specimen height (25 mm). The load–deformation curves exhibit distinct characteristics depending on the loading direction. When loaded in the out-of-layer direction, the specimens exhibit a clear bilinear behavior, yielding at a certain stress level and then continuing to deform without a significant drop in strength. In contrast, when loaded in the in-layer direction, the specimens exhibit higher initial stiffness than in the Z direction, and after reaching the maximum strength, the load-bearing capacity gradually declines. This characteristic is consistently observed regardless of infill density. As shown in Fig. 3(b), there is a significant strength difference between 37% and 60% infill density, whereas the difference between 60% and 75% is minimal. This suggests that compression strength reaches a plateau at approximately 60% infill density.

Fig. 3(c) compares different infill patterns. The results indicate that the triangular infill pattern exhibits higher compression strength than the gyroid pattern, while maintaining a comparable mass. Based on these findings, the triangular infill pattern is adopted for further investigations.

Figure 3. Compression test results for 3D-printed resin.

Figure 4. Photographs of specimens after compression testing, upper: XY-plane view, lower: ZX-plane view.

3.3. Tensile test results

Fig. 5 presents the results of the tensile tests, while Fig. 6 shows photographs of the specimens after testing. Fig. 5(a) compares the tensile behavior in the in-layer and out-of-layer directions for specimens with 37% infill density. The in-layer tensile test exhibits a rounded load–deformation curve without a distinct yield point, unlike the compression test. The tensile strength in the out-of-layer direction is only about one-fifth of that in the in-layer direction, confirming its significantly lower strength. Fig. 5(c) and 5(d) compare the effects of infill density. As the infill density increases, the gradient near the maximum load decreases, resulting in a sharper peak in the characteristic curve. A

clear positive proportional relationship is observed between infill density and tensile strength in the in-layer direction. Fig. 5(b) examines the effect of different infill patterns. For 37% infill density, the gyroid pattern infill pattern exhibits higher tensile strength than the triangular pattern.

Figure 5. Tensile test results for 3D-printed resin.

Figure 6. Photographs of specimens after tensile testing.

3.4. Shear Test Results

Fig. 7 presents the results of the shear tests, while Fig. 8 shows photographs of the specimens after testing. The legend in Fig. 7 includes “ILD-OLS”: in-layer direction on the out-of-layer surface, “OLD-OLS”: out-of-layer direction on the out-of-layer surface. The shear anisotropy of 3D-printed resin was evaluated in three orientations, with experiments conducted under 37% and 60% infill density conditions for each shear plane and direction. The shear strength was lowest in the in-layer direction, while the highest shear strength was observed in the out-of-layer direction on the out-of-layer surface (OLD-OLS). However, the latter exhibited lower stiffness than the other two directions, leading to significant deformation before reaching maximum strength, a trend similar to that observed in the compression test along the out-of-layer direction. Fig. 7(c) shows the relationship between infill density and the average shear strength. For the OLD-OLS case, the yield strength is presented instead of the maximum strength due to the large deformation required to reach peak load, which limits its practical applicability. A nearly proportional relationship between shear strength and infill density is observed.

Figure 7. Shear test results for 3D-printed resin.

Figure 8. Photographs of specimens after shear testing (IFD 60%).

Table 3 summarizes the average values of the mechanical test results. Since the compression strength of PAHT CF15-based 3D-printed resin plateaus at approximately 60% infill density, this density is adopted for joint design considerations. Although tensile strength in the out-of-layer direction and shear strength in the in-layer direction were identified as weak points, the compression and shear strengths were approximately 50–60% of the average values for bamboo (approximately 60–70 N/mm², reported by Nagai [3]). Thus, when applying 3D-printed resin in joint components, it is essential to maximize its high compression strength and strategically design the joint to avoid loading in weak shear directions.

Table 3. Summary of mechanical test results for 3D-printed resin.

Direction	IFD [%]	IFP	f_c [MPa]	f_t [MPa]	Plane-direction	IFD [%]	IFP	f_s [MPa]
OLD	37	Gyroid	2.2	-	ILS	37	Triangular	4.2
	37	Triangular	6.3	6.3		60	Triangular	6.8
	60	Triangular	10.6	-	OLS-OLD	37	Triangular	7.4
	75	Triangular	11.7	-		60	Triangular	11.2
ILD	37	Gyroid	11.1	32.0	OLS-ILD	37	Triangular	5.6*
	37	Triangular	14.6	24.7		60	Triangular	8.8*
	60	Triangular	20.2	35.1				
	75	Triangular	20.5	39.6				

IFD: infill density, IFP: infill pattern, f_c : compression strength, f_t : tensile strength, f_s : shear strength, *yiled strength of f_s

4. Mechanical testing of 3D-printed joints

4.1. Testing methods

This study assumes the application of round bamboo in axially dominant structural systems such as trusses and arches and investigates joints capable of transmitting both tensile and compression axial forces. Fig. 9 illustrates the testing methods for the joints.

Figure 9. Mechanical testing methods for joints designed for axial force transmission.

The compression axial force is transmitted through bearing stress between the cut-end surface of the bamboo culm and the 3D-printed resin. The tensile axial force is transmitted through single-shear

resistance, achieved by fastening the bamboo culm wall to the resin infill inserted into the culm cavity using screws. Additionally, by evenly distributing these fastener connections around the outer perimeter of the bamboo culm, the joint is designed to resist minor secondary bending moments. As shown in Fig. 9, the layering direction of the joint component is oriented perpendicular to the bamboo culm axis, aligning the direction of axial force with the in-layer direction, which exhibits superior tensile and compression strength. Since achieving a perfect fit between the resin infill and the bamboo culm cavity is challenging, this study proposes a three-lobed or cross-shaped cross-section design. This ensures that the resin infill contacts the inner surface of the bamboo culm cavity at three or four points for effective load transmission.

The mechanical tests on the joints include compression tests and single-shear tests on screws. The bamboo specimens used in this study are Moso bamboo (*Phyllostachys edulis*) with two culm diameters of approximately 70 mm and 100 mm. For the compression tests, an additional bamboo specimen is extracted from a nearby section of the same culm to evaluate the compression strength of the bamboo culm itself, in addition to testing the joint specimens. For the single-shear tests on screws, the culm diameter and the edge distance h between the screw and the culm cut-end are set as parameters ($h = 10d, 15d, \text{ and } 20d, d:$ root diameter of screws). Additionally, for the 70 mm diameter specimens, strain gauges are attached circumferentially on the outer surface of the bamboo culm at the screw connection, allowing for the measurement of circumferential strain. For each combination of test conditions, three specimens are tested.

4.2. Compression test results for joints

Fig. 10 presents the stress–deformation relationship obtained from the compression tests on the joints, and Fig. 11 shows the photographs of the specimens after testing. The compression stress of the joint specimens is calculated by dividing the applied load by the cross-sectional area of the bamboo culm end in contact with the resin. For comparison, the figure also includes the compression test results of both the 3D-printed resin (with 60% infill density) and the bamboo culm itself, as described earlier.

Figure 10. Stress–deformation relationship in joint compression tests.

Figure 11. Photographs of specimens after testing.

In all test specimens, the compression strength of the joint specimens falls between that of the bamboo and the resin. The reason why the compression strength of the joint exceeds that of the resin itself is that, in the standalone resin compression test, the resin undergoes uniform compression over its entire

surface. In contrast, during the joint compression test, localized indentation occurs at the contact area between the bamboo culm end and the resin, redistributing the stress and effectively increasing the apparent strength per cross-sectional area. Therefore, the compression capacity of the joint can be conservatively estimated using the mechanical properties of the standalone 3D-printed resin, ensuring a safety margin in structural design.

4.3. Single-shear test results for screws

Fig. 12 presents the results of the single-shear tests on screws, along with photographs of the specimens after testing in Fig. 13. The vertical axis in Fig. 12(a) represents the normalized load per fastener (F_b/dt), where F_b is the load per screw, d and t represent the root diameter of the screw and the thickness of the bamboo culm wall, respectively. Upon examining the cross-sections of the test specimens, it was observed that in some cases, the screws exhibited bending deformation, while in others, they did not. However, in all cases, the screws significantly tilted from their initial perpendicular position and embedded into the resin. The maximum load was reached when a small crack appeared at the contact area between the screw and the bamboo culm wall.

Figure 12. Results of single-shear tests for screws.

Figure 13. Failure modes of dowel-type connections in bamboo culms [5], with photographs of specimens during and after testing.

Additionally, Fig. 12(b) provides an example of a 70 mm diameter bamboo specimen, overlaying the load–deformation relationship with the circumferential strain–deformation relationship near the joint. The results indicate that at the maximum load, the circumferential strain increases sharply. This suggests that the observed cracks are not caused by shear failure but rather by the screws embedding into the bamboo culm wall, causing radial expansion in the fiber-perpendicular (tangential) direction.

The failure modes of dowel-type connections in bamboo culms are classified into three types, as shown in Fig. 13. Among them, the theoretical strength values for failure modes A and C can be determined when the load on the screw acts parallel to the bamboo fibers using the following equations:

$$\text{Failure mode A: } F_{b,A} = 1.1d \cdot t \cdot f_c \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Failure mode C: } F_{b,C} = 1.25 \cdot \frac{\pi \cdot t \cdot 1.1d \cdot f_{t,90}}{2(1 - 1.1d/D)^2} \quad (2)$$

Here, f_c is the compression crushing strength of bamboo in the fiber-parallel direction, and $f_{t,90}$ is the tensile strength of bamboo in the fiber-perpendicular direction. However, since standardized data for f_c and $f_{t,90}$ for Moso bamboo grown in Japan is not available, these values are estimated using the following regression equations with explanation variable culm diameter D [mm] derived from the survey results of Nagai [3]. Additionally, $f_{t,90}$ is assumed to be approximated by the bending strength in the fiber-perpendicular direction, and is determined as the average of $f_{m,90,NS}$ and $f_{m,90,EW}$.

$$f_c = -0.3174D + 90.2 \text{ [N/mm}^2\text{]} \quad (3)$$

$$f_{t,90} \approx \frac{f_{m,90,NS} + f_{m,90,EW}}{2} \text{ [N/mm}^2\text{]} \quad (4)$$

$$f_{m,90,NS} = -0.4185D + 74.2, \quad f_{m,90,EW} = -0.1845D + 33.3 \text{ [N/mm}^2\text{]} \quad (5)$$

Table 4. Comparison of experimental and estimated strength values in single-shear tests for screws.

D-h	70-10d	70-15d	70-20d	100-10d	100-15d	100-20d
D_{av} [mm]	71.9	70.4	76.2	103.5	103.3	97.8
t_{av} [mm]	6.66	5.71	6.88	7.95	7.76	7.39
$F_{b,exp}$ [N]	1766	1783.3	1400.7	2606	2510.7	2915.3
$F_{b,A}$ [N]	1893.6	1704.7	1998.4	2006.8	1960.6	1923.6
$F_{b,exp}/F_{b,A}$		0.88			1.83	
$F_{b,C}$ [N]	2006.7	1824.6	2059.4	1688	1651.4	1696.4
$F_{b,exp}/F_{b,C}$		1.04			1.99	

h: edge distance, $F_{b,exp}$: average of experimental maximum load, $F_{b,A}$, $F_{b,C}$: estimated load by Eq. (1), (2)

D_{av} : average of culm diameter, t_{av} : average of culm wall thickness of specimens

Table 4 presents a comparison between the estimated and experimental values of single-shear strength for each failure mode in the tested specimens. Additionally, Fig. 12 illustrates the estimated strength values for each mode, normalized by the bearing area of the screw ($d \times t$), represented as dashed lines. The calculations were performed using the average culm diameters of 72.8 mm and 101.5 mm for the respective specimens. For the 70 mm culm diameter specimens, the ratio of experimental to calculated values for mode C averages 1.04, indicating good agreement. In contrast, for the 100 mm culm diameter specimens, the ratios for both mode A and C range from approximately 1.8 to 2.0, suggesting that the bamboo used in these specimens exhibited higher strength than expected.

Due to specimen constraints in this study, the strength of the bamboo itself used in the joints could not be directly evaluated. For a comprehensive assessment of joint performance, future studies should conduct mechanical testing of the 3D-printed resin, the joint itself, and the bamboo material as an integrated system.

5. Conclusion

This study evaluated the feasibility of using 3D-printed resin joints in round bamboo (full-culm bamboo) structures by conducting fundamental mechanical tests on the resin and mechanical tests on simple joint configurations.

The results indicate that the compression strength of the resin reaches a plateau at an infill density of approximately 60%, suggesting that the level of density is the most efficient for structural applications. Additionally, the compression and shear strengths of the resin were found to be sufficiently practical for use in bamboo structure joints.

As a preliminary proposal for bamboo-to-bamboo joints, a simple jointing method for transmitting both compression and tensile axial forces was examined. The joint transmitting compression axial force through bearing stress at the bamboo culm cross-section exhibited higher strength than the resin alone. Therefore, the mechanical properties of standalone resin can be used as a conservative estimate for the compression strength of the joint. Furthermore, the single-shear connection using screws between the bamboo culm wall and the 3D-printed resin demonstrated shear resistance comparable to that of wood-based materials of similar thickness, with an ultimate strength per fastener of approximately 1.5–3.0 kN. The failure mode at maximum strength was radial splitting (mode C) at the contact area between the screw and the bamboo culm wall. For the 70 mm diameter bamboo specimens, the experimental results closely matched the strength calculation formula specified in ISO 22156.

Moving forward, the long-term goal is to integrate digital fabrication technology using 3D-print technologies with bamboo structures. Future studies will focus on proposing and validating jointing methods for full-scale structural components, such as bamboo trusses and columns.

Acknowledgements

This study was supported by a research grant from the Maeda Memorial Engineering Foundation (2024) and JSPS KAKENHI (21K14292). The authors would like to express their sincere gratitude for this support.

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